

Chemical engineering and transport phenomena in context

Junjie Chen

Department of Energy and Power Engineering, School of Mechanical and Power Engineering, Henan Polytechnic University, 2000 Century Avenue, Jiaozuo, Henan, 454000, P.R. China

Contributor: Junjie Chen, ORCID: 0000-0002-5022-6863, E-mail address: koncjj@gmail.com

Chemical engineering is the development of processes and the design and operation of plants in which materials undergo changes in their physical or chemical state [1]. Applied throughout the process industries, it is founded on the principles of chemistry, physics, and mathematics. The laws of physical chemistry and physics govern the practicability and efficiency of chemical engineering operations. Energy changes, deriving from thermodynamic considerations, are particularly important. Mathematics is a basic tool in optimization and modeling. Optimization means arranging materials, facilities, and energy to yield as productive and economical an operation as possible [1]. Modeling is the construction of theoretical mathematical prototypes of complex process systems, commonly with the aid of computers. Chemical engineering is as old as the process industries [1]. Its heritage dates from the fermentation and evaporation processes operated by early civilizations. Modern chemical engineering emerged with the development of large-scale, chemical-manufacturing operations in the second half of the 19th century. Throughout its development as an independent discipline, chemical engineering has been directed toward solving problems of designing and operating large plants for continuous production. Manufacture of chemicals in the mid-19th century consisted of modest craft operations. Increase in demand, public concern at the emission of noxious effluents, and competition between rival processes provided the incentives for greater efficiency [1]. This led to the emergence of combines with resources for larger operations and caused the transition from a craft to a science-based industry. The result was a demand for chemists with knowledge of manufacturing processes, known as industrial chemists or chemical technologists. The term chemical engineer was in general use by about 1900 [1]. The demand for plants capable of operating physical separation processes continuously at high levels of efficiency was a challenge that could not be met by the traditional chemist or mechanical engineer. A landmark in the development of chemical engineering was the publication in 1901 of the first textbook on the subject, by George E. Davis, a British chemical consultant [1]. This concentrated on the design of plant items for specific operations. The notion of a processing plant encompassing a number of operations, such as mixing, evaporation, and filtration, and of these operations being essentially similar, whatever the product, led to the concept of unit operations [1]. This was first enunciated by the American chemical engineer Arthur D. Little in 1915 and formed the basis for a classification of chemical engineering that dominated the subject for the next 40 years [1]. The number of unit operations, the building blocks of a chemical plant, is not large. The complexity arises from the variety of conditions under which the unit operations are conducted.

In the same way that a complex plant can be divided into basic unit operations, so chemical reactions involved in the process industries can be classified into certain groups, or unit processes, having common characteristics [1]. This classification into unit processes brought rationalization to the study of process engineering. The unit approach suffered from the disadvantage inherent in such classifications: a restricted outlook based on existing practice. Since World War II, closer examination of the fundamental phenomena involved in the various unit operations has shown these to depend on the basic laws of mass transfer, heat transfer, and fluid flow. This has given unity to the diverse unit operations and has led to the development of chemical engineering science in its own right; as a result, many applications have been found in fields outside the traditional chemical industry [1]. Study of the

fundamental phenomena upon which chemical engineering is based has necessitated their description in mathematical form and has led to more sophisticated mathematical techniques [1]. The advent of digital computers has allowed laborious design calculations to be performed rapidly, opening the way to accurate optimization of industrial processes [1]. Variations due to different parameters, such as energy source used, plant layout, and environmental factors, can be predicted accurately and quickly so that the best combination can be chosen. Chemical engineers are employed in the design and development of both processes and plant items [1]. In each case, data and predictions often have to be obtained or confirmed with pilot experiments. Plant operation and control is increasingly the sphere of the chemical engineer rather than the chemist [1]. Chemical engineering provides an ideal background for the economic evaluation of new projects and, in the plant construction sector, for marketing.

The fundamental principles of chemical engineering underlie the operation of processes extending well beyond the boundaries of the chemical industry, and chemical engineers are employed in a range of operations outside traditional areas [1]. Plastics, polymers, and synthetic fibers involve chemical-reaction engineering problems in their manufacture, with fluid flow and heat transfer considerations dominating their fabrication [1]. The dyeing of a fiber is a mass-transfer problem. Pulp and paper manufacture involve considerations of fluid flow and heat transfer. The nuclear industry makes similar demands on the chemical engineer, particularly for fuel manufacture and reprocessing. Chemical engineers are involved in many sectors of the metals processing industry, which extends from steel manufacture to separation of rare metals. Further applications of chemical engineering are found in the fuel industries [1]. In the second half of the 20th century, considerable numbers of chemical engineers have been involved in space exploration, from the design of fuel cells to the manufacture of propellants [1]. Looking to the future, it is probable that chemical engineering will provide the solution to at least two of the world's major problems: supply of adequate fresh water in all regions through desalination of seawater and environmental control through prevention of pollution.

Transport phenomenon, in physics, is any of the phenomena involving the movement of various entities, such as mass, momentum, or energy, through a medium, fluid or solid, by virtue of nonuniform conditions existing within the medium [2]. Variations of concentration in a medium, for example, lead to the relative motion of the various chemical species present, and this mass transport is generally referred to as diffusion [2]. Variations of velocity within a fluid result in the transport of momentum, which is normally referred to as viscous flow [2]. Variations in temperature result in the transport of energy, a process usually called heat conduction [2]. There are many similarities in the mathematical descriptions of these three phenomena, and the three often occur together physically, as in combustion, where a flowing viscous fluid mixture is undergoing chemical reactions that produce heat, which is conducted away, and that produce various chemical species that inter-diffuse with one another.

In engineering, physics and chemistry, the study of transport phenomena concerns the exchange of mass, energy, charge, momentum and angular momentum between observed and studied systems. While it draws from fields as diverse as continuum mechanics and thermodynamics, it places a heavy emphasis on the commonalities between the topics covered. Mass, momentum, and heat transport all share a very similar mathematical framework, and the parallels between them are exploited in the study of transport phenomena to draw deep mathematical connections that often provide very useful tools in the analysis of one field that are directly derived from the others. The fundamental analysis in all three subfields of mass, heat, and momentum transfer are often grounded in the simple principle that the total sum of the quantities being studied must be conserved by the system and its environment. Thus, the different phenomena that lead to transport are each considered individually with the knowledge that the sum of their contributions must equal zero. This principle is useful for calculating many relevant quantities. For example, in fluid mechanics, a common use of transport analysis is to determine the velocity profile of a fluid flowing through a rigid volume. Transport phenomena are ubiquitous

throughout the engineering disciplines. Some of the most common examples of transport analysis in engineering are seen in the fields of process, chemical, and mechanical engineering, but the subject is a fundamental component of the curriculum in all disciplines involved in any way with fluid mechanics, heat transfer, and mass transfer. It is now considered to be a part of the engineering discipline as much as thermodynamics, mechanics, and electromagnetism.

In physics, transport phenomena are all irreversible processes of statistical nature stemming from the random continuous motion of molecules, mostly observed in fluids. Every aspect of transport phenomena is grounded in two primary concepts: the conservation laws, and the constitutive equations. The conservation laws, which in the context of transport phenomena are formulated as continuity equations, describe how the quantity being studied must be conserved. The constitutive equations describe how the quantity in question responds to various stimuli via transport. Prominent examples include Fourier's law of heat conduction and the Navier–Stokes equations, which describe, respectively, the response of heat flux to temperature gradients and the relationship between fluid flux and the forces applied to the fluid. These equations also demonstrate the deep connection between transport phenomena and thermodynamics, a connection that explains why transport phenomena are irreversible. Almost all of these physical phenomena ultimately involve systems seeking their lowest energy state in keeping with the principle of minimum energy. As they approach this state, they tend to achieve true thermodynamic equilibrium, at which point there are no longer any driving forces in the system and transport ceases. The various aspects of such equilibrium are directly connected to a specific transport: heat transfer is the system's attempt to achieve thermal equilibrium with its environment, just as mass and momentum transport move the system towards chemical and mechanical equilibrium. Examples of transport processes include heat conduction, fluid flow, molecular diffusion, radiation and electric charge transfer in semiconductors. Transport phenomena have wide application. For example, in solid state physics, the motion and interaction of electrons, holes and phonons are studied under "transport phenomena". In chemical engineering, transport phenomena are studied in reactor design, analysis of molecular or diffusive transport mechanisms, and metallurgy.

Fluid mechanics is the science concerned with the response of fluids to forces exerted upon them [3]. It is a branch of classical physics with applications of great importance in hydraulic and aeronautical engineering and chemical engineering [3]. The most familiar fluid is of course water, and an encyclopedia of the 19th century probably would have dealt with the subject under the separate headings of hydrostatics, the science of water at rest, and hydrodynamics, the science of water in motion [3]. The foundations of hydrodynamics, on the other hand, were not laid until the 18th century when mathematicians such as Leonhard Euler and Daniel Bernoulli began to explore the consequences, for a virtually continuous medium like water, of the dynamic principles that Newton had enunciated for systems composed of discrete particles [3]. Their work was continued in the 19th century by several mathematicians and physicists of the first rank, notably G.G. Stokes and William Thomson [3]. By the end of the century explanations had been found for a host of intriguing phenomena having to do with the flow of water through tubes and orifices, the waves that ships moving through water leave behind them, raindrops on windowpanes, and the like. There was still no proper understanding, however, of problems as fundamental as that of water flowing past a fixed obstacle and exerting a drag force upon it; the theory of potential flow, which worked so well in other contexts, yielded results that at relatively high flow rates were grossly at variance with experiment. This problem was not properly understood until 1904, when the German physicist Ludwig Prandtl introduced the concept of the boundary layer [3]. Prandtl's career continued into the period in which the first manned aircraft were developed [3]. Since that time, the flow of air has been of as much interest to physicists and engineers as the flow of water, and hydrodynamics has, as a consequence, become fluid dynamics [3]. The term fluid mechanics, as used here, embraces both fluid dynamics and the subject still generally referred to as hydrostatics.

One other representative of the 20th century who deserves mention here besides Prandtl is Geoffrey Taylor of England [3]. Taylor remained a classical physicist while most of his contemporaries were turning their attention to the problems of atomic structure and quantum mechanics, and he made several unexpected and important discoveries in the field of fluid mechanics [3]. The richness of fluid mechanics is due in large part to a term in the basic equation of the motion of fluids which is nonlinear, namely one that involves the fluid velocity twice over. It is characteristic of systems described by nonlinear equations that under certain conditions they become unstable and begin behaving in ways that seem at first sight to be totally chaotic [3]. In the case of fluids, chaotic behavior is very common and is called turbulence [3]. Mathematicians have now begun to recognize patterns in chaos that can be analyzed fruitfully, and this development suggests that fluid mechanics will remain a field of active research well into the 21st century [3]. Fluid mechanics is a subject with almost endless ramifications, and the account that follows is necessarily incomplete [3]. Some knowledge of the basic properties of fluids will be needed; a survey of the most relevant properties will also be needed.

Fluids are not strictly continuous media in the way that all the successors of Euler and Bernoulli have assumed, for they are composed of discrete molecules [3]. The molecules, however, are so small and, except in gases at very low pressures, the number of molecules per milliliter is so enormous that they need not be viewed as individual entities [3]. There are a few liquids, known as liquid crystals, in which the molecules are packed together in such a way as to make the properties of the medium locally anisotropic, but the vast majority of fluids (including air and water) are isotropic [3]. In fluid mechanics, the state of an isotropic fluid may be completely described by defining its mean mass per unit volume, or density, its temperature, and its velocity at every point in space, and just what the connection is between these macroscopic properties and the positions and velocities of individual molecules is of no direct relevance [3]. A word perhaps is needed about the difference between gases and liquids, though the difference is easier to perceive than to describe [3]. In gases the molecules are sufficiently far apart to move almost independently of one another, and gases tend to expand to fill any volume available to them. In liquids the molecules are more or less in contact, and the short-range attractive forces between them make them cohere; the molecules are moving too fast to settle down into the ordered arrays that are characteristic of solids, but not so fast that they can fly apart [3]. Thus, samples of liquid can exist as drops or as jets with free surfaces, or they can sit in beakers constrained only by gravity, in a way that samples of gas cannot. Such samples may evaporate in time, as molecules one by one pick up enough speed to escape across the free surface and are not replaced. The lifetime of liquid drops and jets, however, is normally long enough for evaporation to be ignored.

There are two sorts of stress that may exist in any solid or fluid medium, and the difference between them may be illustrated by reference to a brick held between two hands [3]. If the holder moves his hands toward each other, he exerts pressure on the brick; if he moves one hand toward his body and the other away from it, then he exerts what is called a shear stress [3]. A solid substance such as a brick can withstand stresses of both types, but fluids, by definition, yield to shear stresses no matter how small these stresses may be. They do so at a rate determined by the fluid's viscosity. This property is a measure of the friction that arises when adjacent layers of fluid slip over one another [3]. It follows that the shear stresses are everywhere zero in a fluid at rest and in equilibrium, and from this it follows that the pressure (that is, force per unit area) acting perpendicular to all planes in the fluid is the same irrespective of their orientation (Pascal's law) [3]. For an isotropic fluid in equilibrium there is only one value of the local pressure consistent with the stated values for density and temperature. These three quantities are linked together by what is called the equation of state for the fluid. For gases at low pressures the equation of state is simple and well known [3]. For other fluids knowledge of the equation of state is often incomplete [3]. Except under very extreme conditions, however, all one needs to know is how the density changes when the pressure is changed by a small amount, and this is described by

the compressibility of the fluid, either the isothermal compressibility or the adiabatic compressibility according to circumstance. When an element of fluid is compressed, the work done on it tends to heat it up [3]. If the heat has time to drain away to the surroundings and the temperature of the fluid remains essentially unchanged throughout, then the isothermal compressibility is the relevant quantity [3]. If virtually none of the heat escapes, as is more commonly the case in flow problems because the thermal conductivity of most fluids is poor, then the flow is said to be adiabatic, and the adiabatic compressibility is needed instead.

Mechanics is the science concerned with the motion of bodies under the action of forces, including the special case in which a body remains at rest [4]. Of first concern in the problem of motion are the forces that bodies exert on one another. This leads to the study of such topics as gravity, electricity, and magnetism, according to the nature of the forces involved [4]. Given the forces, one can seek the manner in which bodies move under the action of forces; this is the subject matter of mechanics proper. Historically, mechanics was among the first of the exact sciences to be developed. Its internal beauty as a mathematical discipline and its early remarkable success in accounting in quantitative detail for the motions of the Moon, Earth, and other planetary bodies had enormous influence on philosophical thought and provided impetus for the systematic development of science [4]. Mechanics may be divided into three branches: statics, which deals with forces acting on and in a body at rest; kinematics, which describes the possible motions of a body or system of bodies; and kinetics, which attempts to explain or predict the motion that will occur in a given situation [4]. Alternatively, mechanics may be divided according to the kind of system studied [4]. The simplest mechanical system is the particle, defined as a body so small that its shape and internal structure are of no consequence in the given problem [4]. More complicated is the motion of a system of two or more particles that exert forces on one another and possibly undergo forces exerted by bodies outside of the system.

The principles of mechanics have been applied to three general realms of phenomena. The motions of such celestial bodies as stars, planets, and satellites can be predicted with great accuracy thousands of years before they occur [4]. (The theory of relativity predicts some deviations from the motion according to classical, or Newtonian, mechanics; however, these are so small as to be observable only with very accurate techniques, except in problems involving all or a large portion of the detectable universe.) As the second realm, ordinary objects on Earth down to microscopic size (moving at speeds much lower than that of light) are properly described by classical mechanics without significant corrections [4]. The engineer who designs bridges or aircraft may use the Newtonian laws of classical mechanics with confidence, even though the forces may be very complicated, and the calculations lack the beautiful simplicity of celestial mechanics [4]. The third realm of phenomena comprises the behavior of matter and electromagnetic radiation on the atomic and subatomic scale [4]. Although there were some limited early successes in describing the behavior of atoms in terms of classical mechanics, these phenomena are properly treated in quantum mechanics.

Classical mechanics deals with the motion of bodies under the influence of forces or with the equilibrium of bodies when all forces are balanced [4]. The subject may be thought of as the elaboration and application of basic postulates first enunciated by Isaac Newton in his *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica* (1687), commonly known as the *Principia* [4]. These postulates, called Newton's laws of motion, may be used to predict with great precision a wide variety of phenomena ranging from the motion of individual particles to the interactions of highly complex systems [4]. In the framework of modern physics, classical mechanics can be understood to be an approximation arising out of the more profound laws of quantum mechanics and the theory of relativity [4]. However, that view of the subject's place greatly undervalues its importance in forming the context, language, and intuition of modern science and scientists. The present-day view of the world and man's place in it is firmly rooted in classical mechanics. Moreover, many ideas and results of classical mechanics survive

and play an important part in the new physics [4]. The central concepts in classical mechanics are force, mass, and motion. Neither force nor mass is very clearly defined by Newton, and both have been the subject of much philosophical speculation since Newton. Both of them are best known by their effects. Mass is a measure of the tendency of a body to resist changes in its state of motion [4]. Forces, on the other hand, accelerate bodies, which is to say, they change the state of motion of bodies to which they are applied. The interplay of these effects is the principal theme of classical mechanics.

Although Newton's laws focus attention on force and mass, three other quantities take on special importance because their total amount never changes [4]. These three quantities are energy, (linear) momentum, and angular momentum [4]. Any one of these can be shifted from one body or system of bodies to another [4]. In addition, energy may change form while associated with a single system, appearing as kinetic energy, the energy of motion; potential energy, the energy of position; heat, or internal energy, associated with the random motions of the atoms or molecules composing any real body; or any combination of the three. Nevertheless, the total energy, momentum, and angular momentum in the universe never changes [4]. This fact is expressed in physics by saying that energy, momentum, and angular momentum are conserved. These three conservation laws arise out of Newton's laws, but Newton himself did not express them [4]. They had to be discovered later. It is a remarkable fact that, although Newton's laws are no longer considered to be fundamental, nor even exactly correct, the three conservation laws derived from Newton's laws, the conservation of energy, momentum, and angular momentum, remain exactly true even in quantum mechanics and relativity [4]. In fact, in modern physics, force is no longer a central concept, and mass is only one of a number of attributes of matter [4]. Energy, momentum, and angular momentum, however, still firmly hold center stage [4]. The continuing importance of these ideas inherited from classical mechanics may help to explain why this subject retains such great importance in science today.

Energy conversion is the transformation of energy from forms provided by nature to forms that can be used by humans [5]. Over the centuries a wide array of devices and systems has been developed for this purpose. Some of these energy converters are quite simple. The early windmills, for example, transformed the kinetic energy of wind into mechanical energy for pumping water and grinding grain. Other energy-conversion systems are decidedly more complex, particularly those that take raw energy from fossil fuels and nuclear fuels to generate electrical power [5]. Systems of this kind require multiple steps or processes in which energy undergoes a whole series of transformations through various intermediate forms [5]. Many of the energy converters widely used today involve the transformation of thermal energy into electrical energy [5]. The efficiency of such systems is, however, subject to fundamental limitations, as dictated by the laws of thermodynamics and other scientific principles [5]. In recent years, considerable attention has been devoted to certain direct energy-conversion devices that bypass the intermediate step of conversion to heat energy in electrical power generation [5]. Recent studies have traced the development of energy-conversion technology, highlighting not only conventional systems but also alternative and experimental converters with considerable potential [5]. These studies delineate their distinctive features, basic principles of operation, major types, and key applications [5]. A discussion of the laws of thermodynamics and their impact on system design and performance is made herein.

Thermodynamics is the science of the relationship between heat, work, temperature, and energy [6]. In broad terms, thermodynamics deals with the transfer of energy from one place to another and from one form to another. The key concept is that heat is a form of energy corresponding to a definite amount of mechanical work [6]. Heat was not formally recognized as a form of energy until about 1798, when Count Rumford (Sir Benjamin Thompson), a British military engineer, noticed that limitless amounts of heat could be generated in the boring of cannon barrels and that the amount of heat generated is proportional to the work done in turning a blunt boring tool [6]. Rumford's observation of

the proportionality between heat generated and work done lies at the foundation of thermodynamics [6]. Another pioneer was the French military engineer Sadi Carnot, who introduced the concept of the heat-engine cycle and the principle of reversibility in 1824 [6]. Carnot's work concerned the limitations on the maximum amount of work that can be obtained from a steam engine operating with a high-temperature heat transfer as its driving force. Later that century, these ideas were developed by Rudolf Clausius, a German mathematician and physicist, into the first and second laws of thermodynamics, respectively [6]. The most important laws of thermodynamics are:

- The zeroth law of thermodynamics. When two systems are each in thermal equilibrium with a third system, the first two systems are in thermal equilibrium with each other. This property makes it meaningful to use thermometers as the third system and to define a temperature scale.
- The first law of thermodynamics, or the law of conservation of energy. The change in a system's internal energy is equal to the difference between heat added to the system from its surroundings and work done by the system on its surroundings.
- The second law of thermodynamics. Heat does not flow spontaneously from a colder region to a hotter region, or, equivalently, heat at a given temperature cannot be converted entirely into work. Consequently, the entropy of a closed system, or heat energy per unit temperature, increases over time toward some maximum value. Thus, all closed systems tend toward an equilibrium state in which entropy is at a maximum and no energy is available to do useful work.
- The third law of thermodynamics. The entropy of a perfect crystal of an element in its most stable form tends to zero as the temperature approaches absolute zero. This allows an absolute scale for entropy to be established that, from a statistical point of view, determines the degree of randomness or disorder in a system.

Although thermodynamics developed rapidly during the 19th century in response to the need to optimize the performance of steam engines, the sweeping generality of the laws of thermodynamics makes them applicable to all physical systems [6]. In particular, the laws of thermodynamics give a complete description of all changes in the energy state of any system and its ability to perform useful work on its surroundings [6]. Classical thermodynamics does not involve the consideration of individual atoms or molecules [6]. Such concerns are the focus of the branch of thermodynamics known as statistical thermodynamics, or statistical mechanics, which expresses macroscopic thermodynamic properties in terms of the behavior of individual particles and their interactions. It has its roots in the latter part of the 19th century, when atomic and molecular theories of matter began to be generally accepted [6]. The application of thermodynamic principles begins by defining a system that is in some sense distinct from its surroundings [6]. For example, the system could be a sample of gas inside a cylinder with a movable piston, an entire steam engine, a marathon runner, the planet Earth, a neutron star, a black hole, or even the entire universe [6]. In general, systems are free to exchange heat, work, and other forms of energy with their surroundings.

A system's condition at any given time is called its thermodynamic state [6]. For a gas in a cylinder with a movable piston, the state of the system is identified by the temperature, pressure, and volume of the gas [6]. These properties are characteristic parameters that have definite values at each state and are independent of the way in which the system arrived at that state [6]. In other words, any change in value of a property depends only on the initial and final states of the system, not on the path followed by the system from one state to another [6]. Such properties are called state functions. In contrast, the work done as the piston moves and the gas expands and the heat the gas absorbs from its surroundings depend on the detailed way in which the expansion occurs [6]. The behavior of a complex thermodynamic system, such as Earth's atmosphere, can be understood by first applying the principles of states and properties to its component parts, in this case, water, water vapor, and the various gases making up the atmosphere [6]. By isolating samples of material whose states and properties can be

controlled and manipulated, properties and their interrelations can be studied as the system changes from state to state.

A particularly important concept is thermodynamic equilibrium, in which there is no tendency for the state of a system to change spontaneously [6]. For example, the gas in a cylinder with a movable piston will be at equilibrium if the temperature and pressure inside are uniform and if the restraining force on the piston is just sufficient to keep it from moving. The system can then be made to change to a new state only by an externally imposed change in one of the state functions, such as the temperature by adding heat or the volume by moving the piston [6]. A sequence of one or more such steps connecting different states of the system is called a process. In general, a system is not in equilibrium as it adjusts to an abrupt change in its environment [6]. For example, when a balloon bursts, the compressed gas inside is suddenly far from equilibrium, and it rapidly expands until it reaches a new equilibrium state [6]. However, the same final state could be achieved by placing the same compressed gas in a cylinder with a movable piston and applying a sequence of many small increments in volume (and temperature), with the system being given time to come to equilibrium after each small increment. Such a process is said to be reversible because the system is at (or near) equilibrium at each step along its path, and the direction of change could be reversed at any point [6]. This example illustrates how two different paths can connect the same initial and final states. The first is irreversible (the balloon bursts), and the second is reversible [6]. The concept of reversible processes is something like motion without friction in mechanics [7]. It represents an idealized limiting case that is very useful in discussing the properties of real systems [8]. Many of the results of thermodynamics are derived from the properties of reversible processes.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] C. Hanson, the Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, Y. Chauhan, E. Rodriguez, and A. Tikkanen. *Chemical engineering*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [2] The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica and E. Gregersen. *Transport phenomenon*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [3] T.E. Faber, A. Augustyn, L. Dixon, E. Gregersen, W.L. Hosch, M. Ray, E. Rodriguez, and the Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica. *Fluid mechanics*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [4] D.L. Goodstein, the Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, D. Broad, E. Gregersen, J. Higgins, W.L. Hosch, R. Pallardy, D. Promeet, S. Singh, and S. Sinha. *Mechanics*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [5] E.B. Woodruff, R.L. Seale, F. Landis, C.R. Russell, R. Wailes, the Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, L. Bonte, A. Augustyn, J.M. Cunningham, E. Rodriguez, and G. Young. *Energy conversion*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [6] G.W.F. Drake, B.A. Schreiber, A. Gaur, E. Gregersen, W.L. Hosch, G. Lotha, D. Promeet, M. Sampaolo, S. Singh, S. Sinha, G. Young, and the Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica. *Thermodynamics*. Encyclopædia Britannica® Online, 2022 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
- [7] J.M. Prausnitz. Molecular thermodynamics: Opportunities and responsibilities. *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, Volume 116, Issues 1-2, 1996, Pages 12-26.
- [8] D. Vitali and P. Grigolini. Chaos, thermodynamics and quantum mechanics: An application to celestial dynamics. *Physics Letters A*, Volume 249, Issue 4, 1998, Pages 248-258.